

41 BACKGROUND

42 The financial sustainability of social security is one of the central concerns of policymakers in ageing
43 societies. Due to the lack of retirement rate adjustment to the steadily increasing life expectancy over
44 time and the parallel fall in fertility, the ratio of pensioners to workers has substantially increased. This
45 has put severe pressures on social insurance pay-as-you-go (PAYGO) systems and public pension
46 schemes [1, 2]. The public pension expenditure in the Organization for Economic Cooperation and
47 Development (OECD) countries has increased by about 2.5 percent of gross domestic product (GDP)
48 from 1990 to 2017, and forecasts project that it will continue to grow [3].

49 In order to achieve the stabilization of public pension spending, most ageing and aged countries are
50 considering (or have already implemented) pension reforms that increase the statutory retirement age
51 and/or eliminate the mandatory retirement age [1, 4]. Although it is widely accepted that delayed
52 retirement promotes the sustainability of social security, some people strongly express their concerns
53 over the new change. One of the main concerns is that the growing number of retirement-age people
54 in the workforce might have a negative effect on the employment of younger people. There is a strong
55 belief that if older workers remain in the job market, new positions would not open up for the young,
56 which would eventually harm the employment of younger people.

57 The notion that keeping older workers in the workforce would have negative consequences for
58 younger workers mainly arises from the lump of labor theory. Economists tend to regard this theory
59 as a “fallacy” because it ignores the possibility of economic adjustment that can create jobs for willing
60 workers in the long run in accordance with supply and demand [5, 6]. However, opponents argue that
61 continued work by older participants can deprive younger people of jobs at least in the short term.
62 The existing empirical evidence is also conflicting. Some researchers [7-12] stress that there is no
63 substitution effect and possibly a complementary effect between older and younger workers; whereas
64 others [13-16] show a negative relationship between the two groups.

65 To our knowledge, no systematic synthesis has been conducted to examine the effects of the recent
66 retirement-age reforms on the employment of younger persons. Without rigorous understanding of
67 the effects of later retirement, the attempts by governments to increase the labor force participation
68 of older workers would aggravate the public’s fear on the unemployment of youth, make it hard to
69 achieve and maintain the financial sustainability of social insurance, and lead to negative attitudes
70 toward older workers by stigmatizing older people as an obstacle to the employment of younger
71 workers [17].

72 In this review, we will assess the effects of governments’ retirement-age reforms on the employment
73 of younger people. We will synthesize studies that estimate the impact of increases in retirement age
74 on the employment of younger people. We will answer the question of whether there is a negative
75 influence, and if so, to what extent, for how long, and in what context the impact may exist. This
76 systematic review will provide comprehensive understanding of labor market consequences of
77 retirement-age reforms.

78

79 METHODS/DESIGN

80 - Protocol and registration

81 Our systematic review protocol was designed in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for

82 Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) guidelines [18] (see details in Additional
83 file 1). We will conduct the review on the basis of this protocol, and will report any important
84 amendments to the protocol in the final review manuscript. This study has been registered with the
85 Open Science Framework (Registration number osf.io/r4ek7).

86 - Objectives

87 The purpose of this systematic review is to assess the effects of governments' retirement-age reforms
88 to facilitate longer working lives on the employment of younger adults. This review will carefully
89 investigate the magnitude, duration, and consistency of the effects over different levels and subgroups
90 to provide rigorous evidence to policymakers.

91 - Types of studies

92 This review will include studies that quantitatively assess the impact of governments' retirement-age
93 reforms to increase the employment of older people on the employment of younger persons. In order
94 to answer the research question, whether there are any negative effects of retirement-age reforms on
95 the employment of younger people, studies merely look at the relationship between the employment
96 of younger and older adults without assessing the impact of governments' retirement-age reforms will
97 be excluded. Studies analyzing the effects of policy interventions aiming at early retirement will be
98 also excluded.

99 We will include studies whose outcome variables are related to the employment of any age groups
100 younger than the older age group. This will include the age groups of people not only first entering the
101 labor force but also in their prime working lives. We will include natural experiment designs such as:
102 interrupted time-series analyses, before-and-after studies, instrumental variable estimation methods,
103 difference-in-differences estimation methods, and other statistical analyses of economic models.

104 - Types of participants

105 According to the International Labour Organization (ILO) and OECD definitions, the conventional
106 categories of age groups in the labor force are: the young (15-24 or 20-24); the prime-aged (25-54);
107 and the old (55-64, or 55 and above). However, how to define the age groups may differ based on
108 research timing, country, and context. We will accept the deviation from the conventional age
109 categories if there is a reasonable reason. We will include studies that use age as a variable of interest
110 in the reforms and the response to the reforms.

111 - Types of interventions

112 Any retirement-age reforms enacted by a government to increase labor force participation of older
113 adults will be included. This includes, but not limited to, increasing the statutory retirement age,
114 increasing the age of conditional eligibility for old-age pension, increasing the age of absolute eligibility
115 for old-age pension, and eliminating the mandatory retirement age. The definition and type of
116 retirement age varies depending on the pension system and national law in each country. A study
117 should clearly describe the old-age pension scheme and/or the retirement-age reform in order to be
118 included in this review.

119 - Types of outcome measures

120 The outcome variable in this review is the employment of younger population just entering the labor

121 market and/or in their prime working lives. We will include any outcome measures related to
122 employment, such as employment rates, unemployment rates, and labor force participation rates.

123 We will also include various levels and timings of outcomes. The impact of retirement-age reforms may
124 be evaluated at different levels, from the cross-national or national levels to the firm or individual
125 levels. In addition, the timing of outcomes can vary from short term (within a year) to long term (over
126 20 years). This review will exhaustively include studies that evaluate interventions at any level and
127 timing.

128 - Search strategy

129 A full search will be conducted in five electronic databases: EconLit, ABI/INFORM Collection, Business
130 Source Complete, Web of Science Core Collection, and SCOPUS. We will include only English in our
131 searches. No date limits will be applied. The search strategies for all databases are in Additional file 2.

132 We will include peer-reviewed journal articles only. Excluded will be non-peer-reviewed publications,
133 other grey literature, qualitative studies, reviews, and other syntheses. Peer-reviewed articles are
134 already verified via the academic process, thus they are more likely to be a high-quality source in terms
135 of data quality and methodology applied [19]. Considering the complexity of research designs and the
136 difficulty of measuring study quality in this economic research field, this criterion will give more
137 credibility to the results in our review.

138 Our search strategy was reviewed by an experienced librarian at Bar-Ilan University.

139 **Inclusion Criteria**

- 140 1. Language: English
- 141 2. Participants: Working age population divided into age groups of younger and older workers
- 142 3. Study design: Natural experiment designs (including interrupted time-series analyses, before-
143 and-after studies, instrumental variable estimation methods, difference-in-differences
144 estimation methods, and other statistical techniques)
- 145 4. Intervention: Any retirement-age reforms enacted by a government to promote labor force
146 participation of older persons (including increasing the statutory retirement age, increasing
147 the age of conditional eligibility for old-age pension, increasing the age of absolute eligibility
148 for old-age pension, and eliminating the mandatory retirement age)
- 149 5. Outcome: Any outcome measures related to employment of younger people (e.g.
150 employment rates, unemployment rates, and labor force participation rates); both short-term
151 and long-term outcomes; and all levels of outcomes (including cross-national, national,
152 industry, firm, and individual levels)

153 **Exclusion Criteria**

- 154 1. Excluded studies: Qualitative studies, reviews, and other syntheses
- 155 2. Excluded interventions: Retirement-age reforms aiming at decreasing labor force participation
156 of older adults, and interventions that do not directly influence the legal retirement age
- 157 3. Excluded publications: Non-peer-reviewed publications and other grey literature (including
158 non-academic journals and reports)

159 - Data management and extraction

160 Two authors (SK and ML) will independently carry out the title/abstract screening, full-text review, data
 161 extraction, and risk of bias assessment. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion in
 162 consultation with the other reviewers (DG and LA). Data will be managed via Covidence software [20]
 163 and extracted using a customized extraction form (see Table 1). We will produce a PRISMA diagram
 164 [21] to describe the flow of studies throughout the stages of the review. If there is any ambiguous
 165 information regarding the extracted data, we will contact the authors of the original studies to obtain
 166 further details.

167 **Table 1.** Data extraction fields

General information	Authors
	Year of publication
	Title
	Journal
	Country of study
Study characteristics	Study aim
	Study level (e.g. individual, firm, national, and cross-country level)
	Study duration (including pre-intervention period and follow-up)
Study participants	Description of data used for the study (including sample size)
	Inclusion/exclusion criteria for study participants
	Age category (and justification for any deviations)
Intervention characteristics	Description of public pension schemes or retirement-age reforms
	Intervention duration and timing
Outcome variables	Outcome variables included
Data analysis	Type of analyses conducted
	Management of confounding factors
Results	Baseline and post-intervention results
	Estimates of effect (including by time, subgroup, etc.)
	Main conclusion

168

169 - Quality assessment and risk of bias

170 We will assess included studies using the National Institutes of Health (NIH) quality assessment tools
 171 [22]. Most assessment tools are developed for the appraisal of clinical papers, and, as far as we know,
 172 no specific guidelines or tools exist for the assessment of economic research without health-related
 173 outcomes. Among the existing tools, those from the NIH will be appropriate in this review because
 174 they are easily interpretable across various study designs. We anticipate that only few studies will
 175 include control groups in this macro-level, policy evaluation research. The NIH tools will be easier to
 176 apply to those studies that do not have control groups and health-related outcomes. Each tool has 8-
 177 14 items depending on the study design to appraise potential defects in study methods or
 178 implementation. This includes “sources of bias (e.g., patient selection, performance, attrition, and
 179 detection), confounding, study power, the strength of causality in the association between
 180 interventions and outcomes, and other factors” [22]. We will generate a summary table for each study
 181 with an overall rating of either “good,” “fair,” or “poor” quality based on the NIH guidelines. Studies
 182 rated a “poor” quality will be excluded from the final results, unless there is no other better-quality
 183 evidence available.

184 - Strategy for analysis

185 Based on the search results, we will decide on whether to conduct a meta-analysis. We anticipate that
186 study participants, retirement-age reforms, and economic models are likely to be heterogeneous. We
187 will consider generating estimates of effect by gender, intervention type, or methodological similarity
188 to check the possibility of conducting a meta-analysis. If there are at least two studies that are
189 sufficiently similar and can be meaningfully pooled, we will perform a meta-analysis using either fixed
190 or random effect models [23]. We will test variability across studies using the I^2 statistic [24]. As guided
191 by the Cochrane Handbook, I^2 statistic more than 50% will be regarded as substantial heterogeneity
192 [25].

193 Where appropriate and feasible, a meta-analysis will be employed; otherwise, we will conduct a
194 narrative review and a structured synthesis of the evidence. We will synthesize the labor market effects
195 based on the levels of study (e.g. cross-national, national, firm, and individual level), the duration of
196 study (e.g. short-term and long-term effects), and/or moderators (e.g. gender, job sector, and job
197 quality). Considering the availability of data, we will make a final decision on the detailed synthesis
198 plan.

199 - Missing data

200 If important data are missing, we will contact the corresponding author of the study via email. After
201 two attempts to contact authors, if data cannot be obtained, they will be marked as “missing” in the
202 data extraction form.

203 - Assessment of reporting bias

204 If there are more than 10 studies in the meta-analysis, we will examine reporting biases using funnel
205 plots. Asymmetry will be investigated using a visual assessment. If we identify evidence of publication
206 biases, exploratory analyses will be conducted to verify asymmetry.

207

208 DISCUSSION

209 The purpose of this systematic review is to assess the effects of governments’ retirement-age reforms
210 to facilitate longer working lives on the employment of younger adults. We expect that this review will
211 enable policymakers to measure relative gains and losses on retirement-age reforms when taking
212 policy actions, and to prepare for the potential impact of the reforms in advance. This review will also
213 identify gaps in the existing evidence to inform the future research direction.

214

215 ADDITIONAL FILES

216 **Additional file 1:** PRISMA-P (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analyses Protocols) 2015
217 checklist: recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol. (DOC 32 kb)

218 **Additional file 2:** Search terms and strategies (DOC 19 kb)

219

220

221 Abbreviations:

222 GDP: Gross Domestic Product; GRADE: Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation;
223 ILO: International Labour Organization; NIH: National Institutes of Health; OECD: Organization for Economic
224 Cooperation and Development; OSF: Open Science Framework; PAYGO: Pay-As-You-Go; PRISMA: Preferred
225 Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

226

227 Acknowledgements:

228 We would like to thank a librarian, Yodfat Taase, at Bar-Ilan University who provided advice in developing the
229 search strategy.

230

231 Funding:

232 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
233 under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 764632.

234

235 Availability of data and materials:

236 Not applicable

237

238 Authors' contributions:

239 SK and LA conceived the idea for the systematic review. SK led the design of the protocol and methodology,
240 devised the search strategy, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. DG and LA supervised the design of the
241 protocol and methodology and critically revised the manuscript. All authors have read and approved the final
242 manuscript.

243

244 Ethics approval:

245 Not applicable

246

247 Consent for publication:

248 Not applicable

249

250 Competing interests:

251 None declared

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